

EFFECTIVE COMPETENCY-BASED TRAINING LEARNING ENVIRONMENT TOWARDS CAREER COMPETENCIES AMONGST VOCATIONAL STUDENTS

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Abstract

The gaps between vocational students' skill competencies and the skills demanded by the industries bring major impacts towards the unemployment rate of vocational graduates. However, the mismatch of the competencies between the students and the industrial needs could not be solved through conventional learning methods. Ironically, the career competencies of these students seem to be best developed through the Competency-Based Training (CBT) learning environment. Content analysis was carried out to deliberate the factors that lead to an effective CBT learning environment for students in the technical field. Among the factors are; the source of learning, evaluation, clear objectives, the burden of tasks, good teaching and learning community. Then, the career competencies of vocational students, which consist of personal, technical, networking, self-profile, career exploration, and career control are reviewed, in relations to the factors of the effective CBT learning environment. Finally, a suggestion for future research is discussed.

Keywords: Career development, Competency-based training, Learning environment.

1. Introduction

Competency is defined as a combination of knowledge, skills, and abilities required to perform certain tasks in accordance with the prescribed standard [1]. Boahin et al. [2] stated that competencies include individual capacities in carrying out the tasks and roles in their careers according to the specification set by the industry. Meanwhile, career competency is the ability of individuals to carry out tasks as set out in certain occupations to achieve the industrial needs [3]. Kuijpers and Scheerens [4] acknowledged that factors such as economic and technological changes have led to a widespread and unpredictable career environment.

Current employers are demanding that engineering graduates must have immediate specific skills to be employed where only those who meet the needs and highly skilled graduates will only be shortlisted [5]. This situation caused many engineering graduates to be unemployed. In 2006, 23.6% of technical graduates were unemployed [6], compared to 20.9% in 2015 [7]. According to a report conducted by Dobbs et al. [8], 79% of graduates need helps in finding jobs and as many as 39% of employers in the industry are facing the difficulties in fulfilling the skilled vacancies. Based on the high unemployment rate among engineering graduates, scholars have identified that there is a skill mismatch between the graduates and the requirements of industries [9]. The graduates' workability issue shows that there is a shortage with the skills training program that accompanied the trainee skills training system based on the National Occupational Skill Standard (NOSS).

Competency-Based Training (CBT)

Previous studies have found that Competency-Based Training (CBT) succeeded in providing the basic skills required by most industries. Generic skills incorporated in the general and specific skills required at work are manifested in CBT that enables students to have local and international marketability [10, 11]. CBT is essential to find the compatibility between educational institutions and industries. The standard of competencies that should be achieved by students are set by the industry to meet the needs of certain industrial skills. In Malaysia, the competency standards are set by the National Occupational Skills Standard (NOSS) under the Department of Skills Development (JPK). NOSS has outlined the competencies that are needed by a qualified manpower in a particular field and how to achieve such competence. However, the graduates' employability level is still in a worrying state whereby graduates are facing the problem to get the suitable job that is equivalent to their skills. This shows that there is a lack of the skills training program that involves the trainees, which is the skills training system of NOSS [12]. In terms of the linkage to the industry, the training given is general and not specific to the occupational needs in which, the trainees are given only minimal industry exposure because of the emphasizes on the class-based learning [13].

Generally, the education system uses a time-based conventional approach that focuses on grades to demonstrate success, especially in evaluating cognitive and knowledge achievement. On the other hand, Competency-Based Training (CBT) focuses on training students in the aspects of job-related skills, values, and attitudes. In the CBT curriculum, each competency is placed as the outcome that the student should achieve. Students who achieve the desired competency level may extend beyond the learning module. Any organization and industry will put conditions of work experience during the recruitment process, while those who will enter the world

of work after graduating do not have enough experience and knowledge [14]. But how can they get the work experience while they never work? How would the school or institution build and develop the industry's appropriate and required skills.

2. Methodology

Factors of the effective CBT learning environment were identified through the analyses of selected publications using few keywords such as; effective CBT, learning environment, and CBT environment. Online literature search engines were used during these processes. The related articles were chosen from the database of Sage Publications, Science Direct, and Taylor and Francis. This process produced 112 articles but only 75 were used after the screening process in the second phase. 20% of the articles were identified to be associated with vocational students while the remaining articles were associated with higher education in general. Then, these chosen articles were analysed. A literature review of published articles was undertaken to identify the elements of vocational students' career competencies. Students' career competencies were discussed in relations to the effective CBT learning environment.

2.1. Effective CBT learning environment

According to the Environment-Individual Theory, a satisfying compatibility can be achieved if there is an interaction between the individual (student) and the environment (learning) [15]. Previous studies have identified several factors that lead to an effective CBT learning environment, which are the source of learning [16-18], evaluation [17, 19, 20], burden of tasks [19], good teaching [16-19], clear objectives [19] and the learning community [21].

2.2. Source of learning

Learning resources are all forms of infrastructure and infostructure provided for students. According to Mokhtar et al. [17], the facilities in the learning environment are needed to meet the needs of the curriculum, the learning process, and the students themselves. Learning resources need to be identified according to the learning approach.

2.3. Evaluation

According to Ramsden [16], evaluation is the quality of assessment given to students to generate learning processes that cover the aspects of testing, analysis, proofing and data conclusions. Evaluation is used to evaluate student achievement in accomplishing competency-based learning objectives according to the specifications set by the National Occupational Skills Standard (NOSS). Therefore, educational institutions should provide students with the opportunity to apply knowledge in a real environment using a broad model or simulation.

2.4. Burden of tasks

The burden of tasks is the difficulty and the number of tasks in the learning process. Students are responsible to complete the tasks during the learning process. A lot of assignments will burden students and affects students' achievement [22]. Students feel stressed by the excessive tasks so there is no

room for them to choose their own desired. However, Bandura [23] argued that if students have a high degree of self-efficacy (self-esteem), they will complete the tasks successfully and always believe that the overload and tough tasks are something to learn, understand and control. Similarly, as stated by Dawis [15], the more challenging the assignment will be, the students will become more proficient. However, to successfully carry out such a task, students need to be supported and motivated by a good environment.

2.5. Good teaching

According to Ramsden [16], good teaching is the quality of teaching that teachers teach. Good teaching is when learning outcomes can be achieved. In the context of this study, learning outcomes are based on competencies. Teachers need to have expertise in implementing competency-based learning processes. The learning process will be more effective if there is a conversation or communication between the students and the teacher. Good teaching also depends on the clarity of objectives during the learning process. In a study by Smith and Bath [24], the quality of instructions and programs is an important factor in determining student learning outcomes. A good lesson will give students the satisfaction they enquire. A competent teacher in the specific field will encourage students to learn deeply (deep learning approach). The satisfaction that the students acquire during the learning process will provide an effective learning experience and this will also enhance the achievement of student competence in the areas they are interested in. Brown [25] referring to the Person-Environment Theory, the interaction between the individual (student) and the environment (learning) will complement one another to achieve a satisfying compatibility. Student satisfaction will exist if the student's requirement is met. Therefore, it is important for a teacher to improve teaching techniques.

2.6. Clear objectives

A clear objective refers to the purpose in which, each learning process is clearly stated to the student. This indicator is measured by looking at whether the student has been given an explanation about the competencies they need to achieve [16]. Mokhtar et al. [17] also pointed out that clear objectives influence the competencies that students will achieve in which, the students can actively engage in the learning process. This is because students are clear and understand what they will learn. Knowledge associated with the workplace skills enables students to understand and see how their knowledge is applied [3, 26]. This means that the curriculum that integrates competencies needs to provide learning objectives in the real situation. The objective of the learning is then transformed into a learning outcome through the competencies attained [27].

2.7. Learning community

The sixth factor is the learning community that refers to the interaction between students in a learning environment with teachers, industry, and educational institutions. According to Smith and Bath [24], the learning community is a group of students who emphasize social interaction and cooperation between students. Having a good learning community will influence students' learning approaches either through 'surface learning approach' or 'deep learning approach'. The learning approach chosen by the students will influence their achievement and consequently

motivate them. The study by Mokhtar et al. [17] also acknowledged that the learning community in the learning environment affects the students' learning approach. In this study, the learning community shows a negative correlation to the surface learning approach. This means that if the learning community is not good, it will encourage students towards the surface learning approach. However, if the learning community is very satisfying in the learning environment, the student will be pushed towards the deep learning approach.

3. Discussion

Employment opportunities are becoming increasingly critical to the needs of industries that require the provision of the immediate workforce from educational institutions. However, career competencies vary by industry, discipline, and individual. In fact, according to Voorhees [1], differences in individual traits and characters will provide different learning experiences. Due to these differences, some students find it difficult to determine the knowledge and skills they need to learn. Therefore, it is pivotal to have CBT learning environment as a career guide for students. Students' career competencies are divided into six different fields, which are the personal (motivation), technical, networking, self-profile, career exploration and career control. CBT learning environment seems to be the most effective way for students to excel in their career competencies.

3.1. Personal

Personal is refer to the intrinsic and extrinsic motivation of an individual. It is the extent, to which an individual is competent to respond to motivation in his or her career [3] or the extent, to which individuals use motivation in their career development. The source of learning (infrastructure and infostructure) play an important role in motivating students to learn and explore their career because the learning sources shorten their time in carrying out tasks or searching for information. A good teaching in CBT learning environment motivates students in their career exploration. Students are motivated by competent teachers that encourage them to learn deeply. Similarly, when students are given excessive or difficult tasks, it will motivate them to carry out the tasks with positive attitudes, like taking them as challenges that will increase their knowledge and skills.

3.2. Technical

It is crucial for vocational students to be proficient not only in theory but also in their technical skills. Students need to know the knowledge and skills they should master in their career. A good infrastructure, like the up-to-date or latest equipment and machines, plays an important role for the students to master the appropriate skills needed in their career. Students learn the skills better in a real setting like using a simulator or Augmented Technology (AR). Besides that, a good evaluation system by NOSS will ensure the students master the skills effectively.

3.3. Networking

The network is the interaction and communication in which, the individual knows the competences of other individuals. They need to know their referrals in their career because individuals build a network of internal and external working environments to assist in their career development. In other words, interpersonal

knowledge and skills are vital to have a good networking [3]. Thus, the interactions between students in the learning community with teachers, industries, and educational institutions are pivotal in developing their career.

3.4. Self-profile

Self-profile refers to how the students present themselves in the working environment. The students need to know how to stand out in their careers. In this sense, students need to have a good career management skill, which encompasses specific discipline or career-related skills and generic skills [28]. Generic skills included teamwork, communication skill, critical thinking and decision-making skill, entrepreneurship skill, leadership skill, information management skill and life-long learning, and ethics and moral. Thus, the clear objectives in the CBT learning environment provide students with a clear self-profile that can be improved and added until they achieve their target. Evaluation in CBT is also essential for self-profile in which, it shows the level of competencies of a student in specific technical skills.

3.5. Career exploration

According to Kuijpers and Scheerens [4], career exploration refers to an individual's competence to explore the work/ industry/ workplace environment. This involves behaviour towards career competencies such as 'know-how' and 'proactive behaviour'. Career exploration also determines how individuals develop their potential in the development of their careers [3]. Individuals need to know the opportunities and know how to create opportunities in their careers. In career exploration, the source of learning and networking are very important. Students need infrastructure to explore their career prospects. Good teachings will help students to know industries better and help them to build their career. This is because experienced teachers who are expert in their field will give a clear picture of the industries and guide the students in their career exploration process. Students also should make their burden of tasks as the opportunities for them to explore their career path.

3.6. Career control

Career control is a plan for an individual career. Kuijpers and Scheerens [4] states that career control is the competencies in planning and acting on individual learning and career processes towards achieving career goals. CBT learning environment plays an important role towards career control of vocational students in which, the students need to have clear objectives of their lessons because each lesson provides them with the learning based on their career field. Students also need to have good teachings to guide them in planning their career path.

4. Implication of CBT

The used of outcome-based approach that incorporated in CBT could increase the career competencies of vocational students. Furthermore, the evaluation that been used in the CBT is based on the competencies. CBT ensures that the subjects that been taught to vocational students are parallel with the industrial markets and the skills learned by the students are match with the skills needed by the industries.

5. Conclusion

CBT is an important part of the career development of vocational students because their career competencies largely depend on the learning environment. The rapidly changing technology and the current unstable economic conditions have changed the situation in some industries. The supply and demand in the industries is a major issue. Demand for workers in some industries is increasing, but the supply of labour from educational institutions is still incapable of accommodating the industrial needs. Therefore, the six career competencies are suggested as a career guide for the effective CBT learning environment and to be incorporated in the competency standards. The inequality of skills and knowledge between educational institutions and industries is also a concern. Future research should take into consideration numerical study of the contribution of CBT learning environment towards skill competencies required by the industries.

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